

Mechanism of Low Temperature Shift Reaction and the Principles of Selection of Catalyst Constituents

P. N. MUKHERJEE, P. K. BASU and S. K. ROY

Central Fuel Research Institute, P. O. F.R.I., Dist. Dhanbad, Bihar

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A mechanism has been proposed for low temperature shift reaction on ZnO-CuO catalysts, in terms of donor and acceptor type of active sites. It is based on data on adsorption of CO and H₂O as well as electrical conductivities of doped and undoped oxides of Cu and Zn.

FROM literature it is observed that the major constituents of L. T. shift reaction catalysts are oxides of Copper and Zinc¹⁻⁵. In an earlier paper⁶ it was shown how the activity of cupric oxide as a catalyst constituent depends on its electronic properties and that CO undergoes chemisorption on cupric oxide and is held as positive CO⁺ ions. In a subsequent publication⁷ it has been shown that water undergoes dissociative chemisorption on ZnO, the other constituent of the L. T. shift catalyst. The chemisorption of water was found to be followed by liberation of gaseous hydrogen and the experimental findings were interpreted to suggest that water chemisorption leads to the formation of oxygen and hydrogen ions and the latter get attached to quasi-free electron present in the ZnO lattice and are liberated as gaseous hydrogen. Based on these two sources of information, a plausible mechanism for low temperature shift reaction is presented as follows :

The reaction comprises three major steps, namely,

- (i) dissociative chemisorption of water on ZnO leading to the formation of oxygen and hydrogen ions followed by liberation of hydrogen as gas.
- (ii) Chemisorption followed by oxidation of CO on CuO.
- (iii) Migration of oxygen from ZnO to CuO lattice.

In *n*-type ZnO semiconductor, an excess of zinc metal is present in the form of zinc ions in interstitial positions as Zn¹⁺ or Zn²⁺ and an equal number of quasi-free electrons (-)⁸.

The chemisorption of H₂O on zinc oxide will proceed as follows :

Zinc oxide lattice which has thus acquired extra oxygen ions will readily tend to lose them. Thus oxygen will be able to migrate over to copper oxide which is in intimate association⁹ with ZnO in L. T. shift catalyst.

Chemisorption of CO on *p*-type cupric or cuprous oxide may proceed as follows :

Thus, if O from zinc oxide as shown in the last step of (1) migrates to copper oxide as shown in the last step of (2) the catalyst (ZnO and CuO) is restored to the original condition. Thus electrical neutrality of the system as well as the dynamic equilibrium is maintained. It should, however, be noted that CO may pick up oxygen either from cupric oxide lattice as shown in equation (2) and get the loss replenished through migration of oxygen from zinc oxide or it may react only with that oxygen which comes over to copper oxide by migration. In either case, the final result is the same. The latter mechanism finds support from the work of Cotton and Fensham¹⁰ who have shown that CO⁺ is not directly chemisorbed on Cu⁺ sites as chemisorption occurs only on previously adsorbed oxygen layer.

The mechanism postulated above is essentially similar to that proposed earlier by Ghosh *et al.*⁹. These authors based their conclusions on a different set of experimental observations, namely, ESR and electrical conductivity data. Alternative mechanisms have also been proposed by other workers, primarily from kinetic studies¹¹. Based mainly on I. R. data an altogether different reaction mechanisms has been proposed¹² where it was postulated that H₂O is held on the surface of zinc oxide as OH radicals and that reaction occurs between OH radicals and CO. However, this mechanism does not take into

account the fact that even in absence of CO, water adsorption alone leads to the liberation of H₂ on the surface of zinc oxide, as has been shown by the present authors⁷.

From the reaction mechanism postulated above, it is tempting to infer that catalyst for low temperature shift reaction should comprise a suitable combination of both *p* and *n*-type semi-conductor oxides. This view finds support from the data on the composition of catalysts as reported by various workers¹⁻⁵ and also from experimental data presented by the authors (vide Table I). It is however significant that a number of catalyst formulations as reported in the literature comprise a mixture of only *p*-type oxides¹³⁻¹⁶ such as CoO, CuO, Cr₂O₃ and Mn⁺⁺. This anomaly may be explained if we assume that of the two *p*-type oxides one provides the donor and the other acceptor sites. This is possible if the relative Fermi potentials in the oxides and the gases undergoing chemisorption are favourable to permit electron transfer as postulated in the mechanism.

Experimental

The following catalysts which comprise a mixture of *p* and *n* type semi-conductor oxides were prepared and tested for L.T. shift conversion in a flow reactor (i) Cr₂O₃ and TiO₂, (ii) NiO and Fe₂O₃ and (iii) CoO and TiO₂. For all the formulations, atomic ratio of *p* : *n* type oxides was as 0.4 : 1. The catalysts were prepared by co-precipitation as carbonates from the respective nitrate solutions followed by filtration, drying and curing at 400°. Before the test runs, the catalysts were inducted in a flow reactor in a current of a mixture of steam and gas (CO and H₂ in equal proportion) in 10 : 1 ratio at 220° for 30 hrs at a space velocity of 600 cc/gm/hr. For test runs, a mixture of gas containing 7% CO and 93% H₂ was used and the reactions were carried out at two different temperature, namely, 220° and 350° with a space velocity of 600. The ratio of gas to steam was 1 : 1 in all the tests. The efficiency of the catalysts was measured in terms of the p. c. conversion of CO to CO₂ at the end of twenty-four hrs of continuous run. The results are presented in Table I.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF CATALYST CONSTITUENTS ON THE ACTIVITY OF L.T. SHIFT REACTION CATALYSTS

Catalyst	Temp.	p. c. conversion
Cr ₂ O ₃ + TiO ₂	220°C	60
CoO + TiO ₂	"	70
NiO + Fe ₂ O ₃	"	68
Cr ₂ O ₃ + TiO ₂	350°C	96
CoO + TiO ₂	"	45
NiO + Fe ₂ O ₃	"	67

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